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FLUID DYNAMICS PROJECT LABORATORY – CONVERSION TO AN ONLINE COURSE WITH INTERACTIVE 3D MODELS TO ENHANCE LEARNING SUCCESS

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ABSTRACT

The Technische Universität Berlin offers the annual orientation program MINTgrün/STEMgreen for prospective students. The department of Fluid System Dynamics participates with a fluid mechanics project laboratory, which connects hydraulic turbomachinery with the sustainable use of resources and the role of renewable energy to our society. In winter semester 2020/21, the project laboratory was thematically extended. The module now deals with the working principle and design of hydraulic pumps, in addition to the established wind and water turbines. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the laboratory was shifted online and enhanced with digital teaching concepts to create new learning experiences.

The project lab's goal is to introduce students to multifaceted aspects of pump-related engineering and social challenges. In groups of four to five, students are given the opportunity to design a water pump by using typical engineering software. To recognize approaches to a solution, necessary knowledge from the field of fluid

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mechanics is provided, which is supplemented with relevant content of project management. Interactive 3D models were developed and used to illustrate technically complex components and to encourage independent online learning. In addition, students are introduced to classic engineering tools to solve problems. The individually designed machine parts are then 3D printed and tested on a specially developed test rig. In the process, relationships to other engineering disciplines are continuously established and discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Outline of the MINTgrün/ STEMgreen orientation program

The MINTgrün/ STEMgreen program was established in 2012 at the Technische Universität Berlin. The intention of this two-semester orientation program is to give prospective students the opportunity to explore various topics and areas of interest to subsequently make a well-founded choice of study. Topics of the MINT area are mathematics, computer science, natural sciences and technology. The gained theoretical knowledge is supplemented by practical laboratories. One of these labs is the fluid dynamics project laboratory, which is led by the fluid system dynamics department.

1.2 Composition of the fluid dynamics project laboratory

The one semester project gives students the opportunity to gain practical experience in the field of fluid machinery. In addition to the established topics, such as wind and water turbines, the design and construction of a pump impeller has been added to the portfolio. At the beginning of the project, the students learn to create a project-accompanying schedule from the field of project management. This is followed by an introduction to the necessary theoretical principles in the field of fluid mechanics. Simultaneously to the familiarization with these basics, an introduction to the required software programs takes place. The time schedule and the necessary calculations are made with MS Excel. The subsequent impeller design as a CAD model is developed with SolidWorks, which the students receive a two-week introduction for. The created models are then 3D printed and tested at the department on a test rig. However, due to the pandemic, the use of the test rig is only possible in small groups and depending on the local COVID-19 incidence. Therefore this part could not take place in presence in the last semester. At the end of the project a final presentation and a project report of the respective groups are mandatory.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Transition to an online format

As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, the fluid dynamics project laboratory has been converted to an online format. Lecture content is delivered in Zoom meetings. In these digital lectures, students have the opportunity to discuss the content

together and ask questions. Following the lectures, students move into a group work phase. Zoom offers digital group workspaces, so called break-out sessions. In these sessions, the individual groups can work on their projects and exchange ideas with the project supervisors. In comparison to past semesters, which is explained in detail in [1], the structure of the project was adapted. Scientific writing and presentation skills are already introduced halfway through the project. From this point on, the students present their respective group status in short interim presentations. The aim is to stimulate the exchange between the students and to reduce the distances that have arisen due to the online format. Table 1 presents the adapted schedule of the project lab.

Table 1. composition of the fluid dynamics project laboratory

Duration	Topic	Student assignments
- two sessions	- introduction - project management	- project introduction - group organisation - timeline planning with MS Excel
- four sessions	- fluid mechanics - turbo-machine - impeller design	- fundamental and advanced calculations with MS Excel - comprehensive impeller design
- two sessions	- CAD (computer aided design)	- software introduction - basic 3D modelling - impeller designing
- two sessions	- scientific writing - Presentations	- guidelines for scientific writing - Introduction in MS Word/ Power Point - interim presentation and report
- two sessions	- define boundary conditions for student's own impeller - 3D printing impellers - test rig setup	- each group calculates and designs a distinct impeller - post-processing of impeller models - test run on the test rig
- one session	- presentation - report	- final report and presentation

During the introductory phases in the subject of fluid mechanics and fluid machines, complicated relationships used to be illustrated very well using a large number of

fluid machines and impellers in the laboratory of the department of fluid system dynamics. For the use in online formats, interactive 3D models were developed as an alternative.

2.2 Compilation of interactive 3D Models

In order to be able to present complex content as clearly as possible to students in online formats, more suitable solutions were sought. In [2] possible concepts using 3D models to support interactive learning methods for students are described. After a short evaluation the software program Sketchfab was chosen. Sketchfab is, according to its own specifications, a 3D publishing tool with which models can be accessed via any browser. Sketchfab is already used by various universities and museums to provide 3D models of teaching content or exhibits. For example, the University of Dundee's d'Arcy Thompson Zoology Museum has created a digital compilation of various species using Sketchfab [3]. Furthermore, a positive impact of 3D models used in teaching in the field of medicine can be found in [4], where not only the influence of web-browser models, but also virtual reality models were compared.

Implementing Sketchfab models into an existing course on the learning platform of the Technische Universität Berlin (ISIS) is very intuitive. When interacting with the provided models, students have the possibility to freely scale and rotate them. Furthermore, annotations can be added directly to the models. Fig. 2a shows a model of an impeller with a partially cut-out shroud. Through the cutout, students can gain insight into the otherwise hidden blade channel. In addition, five annotations have been added to this model: shroud, hub, blade, leading edge and trailing edge. With the help of Bender, a freely accessible software program, animations can also be added to the model. For example, the rotation of an impeller in a housing can be shown this way.

Fig. 1. Radial impeller with partially cut-out shroud

3 RESULTS

In the course of the teaching transformation due to the COVID-19 pandemic, a conversion from presence to digital formats was developed. The evaluation of the students took place in a final feedback meeting. Classroom sessions were converted into Zoom sessions and Zoom break out sessions, which were very well received by the students. Even after completing all tasks, most students used this platform to discuss the further course of the project. The cooperation in the groups worked extraordinarily well. In the feedback discussions, the 3D models created were also rated as very helpful. None of the students had any problems with interaction or access. Based on this assessment, further 3D content will be gradually developed and made available in the coming semesters.

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